

Deliverable 2.3

Report on potential risks of DTs in public administration

The Framework Programme for Research & Innovation
Research and Innovation actions (RIA)

ETAPAS

ETHICAL TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION
SERVICES

Grant Agreement Number: 101004594

[H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020] Socioeconomic and Cultural
Transformations in the context of the fourth industrial revolution

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List of definitions & abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
DT	Disruptive Technology
DTA	Disruptive Technology Application
PA	Public Administration
PS	Public Sector
WP	Work Package

The ETAPAS Consortium consists of:

Logo	Organisation acronym and name	Country
	MEF – Ministero dell’Economia e delle Finanze	Italy
	PwC – PricewaterhouseCoopers Public Sector Srl	Italy
	2021.AI – 2021.AI APS	Denmark
	SINTEF – SINTEF AS	Norway
	PROKOM – Sem & Stenersen Prokom AS	Norway
	CERTH – Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis	Greece
	IIT – Fondazione Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia	Italy
	LC – The Lisbon Council for Economic Competitiveness ASBL	Belgium
	KTH – Kungliga Tekniska Hoegskolan	Sweden
	CEA – Commissariat à l’énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives	France
	FDG – Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi Onlus	Italy
	MUKA – Municipality of Katerini	Greece
	UNIGRAZ – University of Graz	Austria
	KI – Karolinska Institutet	Sweden

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1. Executive Summary

This report aims at identifying foreseeable risks that may be associated with the introduction of disruptive technologies in the public sector. It will be the basis for further analysis in the ETAPAS project, in particular the development of means to operationalize and measure the various types of risk. The report begins with a short clarification of some central concepts that we refer to. This is followed by a description of the methodology, after which follows the main part of the report, which is a list of the identified risks, grouped in eight major categories.

The major part of this work was performed by Sara Mancini and Noemi Luna Carmeno (PwC), who collected the material and developed the categorization of risks. Based on this material, Sven Ove Hansson (KI) wrote the first draft of this report. It has been reviewed by Barbro Fröding (KTH), Alexandros Zamichos (CERTH), Anna Kougoumtzidou (CERTH), Albert Steiner (UNIGRAZ) and Sarah Domes-Hohl (UNIGRAZ).

1.1 Key concepts

We will write about three central terms in this report: disruptive technology, risk and social impact.

The term *disruptive technology* was introduced by Clayton M. Christensen in a book published in 1997. In his usage, which is still considered to be the standard, the term is only applicable to some of the technologies that have disruptive effects in societies. According to his definition, the disruption has to affect the market and technological companies. Furthermore, the new technology is introduced by new market entrants who focus on marginal or overlooked segments of the market, and have their initial successes in those segments before they gain traction on the rest of the market by providing better function and/or a lower price.¹

However, many scholars use the term in a much more general way and without Christensen's strong focus on manufacturing companies. In this broader sense, a disruptive technology is a technology that has large social consequences. In the (still rather small) literature on disruptive technologies in the public sector, this is the dominant approach, and we will follow that tradition.

The term *risk* has many uses and definitions. The usage in many technical contexts differs drastically from the non-technical language.² In ordinary language, such as newspapers and colloquial discussions, the word "risk" usually refers in a rather vague way to a situation in which it is possible but not certain that some undesirable event will occur. In technical contexts, five of the common usages are:

1. risk = an *unwanted event* which may or may not occur.
2. risk = the *cause* of an unwanted event which may or may not occur.
3. risk = the *probability* of an unwanted event which may or may not occur.
4. risk = the statistical *expectation value* of an unwanted event which may or may not occur.
5. risk = the fact that a decision is made under conditions of *known probabilities* ("decision under risk" as opposed to "decision under uncertainty")³

¹ Clayton M. Christensen (1997) *The innovator's dilemma: when new technologies cause great firms to fail*. Boston, Mass.: Harvard Business School. See also: Christensen, Clayton M., Richard Bohmer, and John Kenagy. "Will disruptive innovations cure health care?" *Harvard business review* 78, no. 5 (2000): 102-112.

² Boholm, M. et al., 2016, "The Concepts of Risk, Safety, and Security: Applications in Everyday Language.", *Risk Analysis*, 36 (2): 320–338.

³ Hansson, Sven Ove, "Risk", *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/risk/>>.

Since this report is an inventory of risks, we have chosen not to limit the concept of risk, but use it in the same wide sense as in most public discussions. This means that risks are occurrences that (1) are commonly considered to be undesirable or have predominantly negative value, and (2) are neither certain to take place nor not to take place. We will be concerned here with the presentation and description of risks rather than with their measurement or quantification.

When we speak of the *social impact* (or social consequence) of some occurrence (such as the introduction of a new technology), we mean something that is an effect of that occurrence, in the sense of standing in a cause-effect relationship with it. This means that the (social) risks associated with a technology form a subset of its social impacts; risks can alternatively be defined as undesirable and uncertain social impacts. In decision-making, both the risks and the benefits (desirable impacts) of a technology have to be taken into account. However, in particular in areas where prominent benefits of a new technology tend to dominate the discussion, it is useful to specifically address the risks, as we do in this report.

1.2 Methodology

This report is the result of a three-step analysis carried out with the scope of the ETAPAS project:

1. A thorough literature review addressing ethical, social and legal aspects of disruptive technologies;
2. The development of a structured framework that categorizes these risks;
3. Review.

Concerning the first step, we carried out a literature review analysing different types of sources, both academic papers and grey literature. This included reports from past and current projects of the ETAPAS partners (e.g. Gov3.0, Big Policy Canvas, E-Sides, AEGIS, Big Data Ocean, Digitranscope, BDVA). Each document was classified and key information extracted and compiled. Overall, more than one thousand documents were reviewed.

The objective of this first step was to get insights on the ethical, social and legal issues that the public sector – public administration and service provision – faces when dealing with disruptive technologies. We then analysed the information extracted from each document with the aim of:

- identifying commonalities to consolidate the most common and important risks and issues related to disruptive technologies;
- spotting potential contradictions among different sources;
- tailoring the risks and issues to the specific context of the public sector.

The result of this analysis was captured in the framework described in this report, which underwent a reviewing process within the ETAPAS consortium to ensure that the results are relevant and adequately based on science and practical experience. The process entailed a first review by the partners working in WP2 and a following review by the other members of the ETAPAS consortium. In the final reworking of the framework, particular emphasis was put on consistency in the description of risks. As mentioned above, the term “risk” can be used both about undesirable outcomes and about causes of such outcomes. We have focused on identifying the undesirable outcomes and in particular avoided to include fairly distant so-called root causes in the framework. We have also excluded “metarisks” such as risks of inadequate knowledge or unclear valuation of risks.

This process allowed us to identify risks associated with disruptive technologies that are relevant in the context of the public sector.

2. Identified risks and their subgroups

We have divided the risks into eight major categories.

2.1 Risks concerning direct interaction with humans

The first category consists of risks arising in the direct interaction between disruptive technologies and human beings.

2.1.1 Replacement of human agency

The implementation of some disruptive technologies might negatively impact the abilities of affected individuals to make free, independent, and well-informed decisions about their lives, thus diminishing their autonomy. Major mechanisms that can lead to this are limitations or biases in the information that people receive. This can for instance be due to the filter bubble effect, to the deliberate dissemination of incorrect or incomplete information, or to the targeting of certain categories of people with specific messages aimed at manipulating their behaviour. In addition, profiling, targeted advertising and other AI-powered techniques can have a profound impact on how we form, and conceive of, our identities and social roles. As some technologies become increasingly capable of analysing the emotional aspects of our personalities, the capacity of such technologies to influence people's behaviour will increase even more in the future.

A recent study by Ujué Agudo and Helena Matute from Universidad de Deusto in Bilbao⁴ shows the influence that algorithms can have on people's decisions and attitudes. They carried out two experiments in the political context to test whether an AI algorithm could manipulate peoples' voting preferences through explicit or covert recommendations or whether, by contrast, people would refuse to follow the algorithm's recommendations, in an attempt to show their independence and freedom. The results shown that the algorithm was able to influence the participants' voting preferences through a simple explicit recommendation while the covert algorithm was not able to influence the participants' voting preferences.

2.1.2 Undisclosed technology use

Disruptive technologies can be programmed to communicate with individuals in a way that gives them the false impression that they are communicating with a human being and not with a machine/a robot (chatbots). When this is done intentionally, it is a form of deception, and even when not intended, it puts users at risk of believing that they are engaging in a different type of communication than they actually are. In general, undisclosed use of disruptive technology puts users at risk of severely misunderstanding the nature of the interaction.

2.1.3 Exclusion of individuals

Unless a new technology is specifically designed to be usable for the variations in physical and mental functioning in the population, there is a considerable risk that the technology will exclude parts of the population. Similarly, technology that requires access to high-quality electronic communication can exclude people who lack such access. There is also a risk of excluding individuals who are less tech orientated, which, in the longer run, contributes to entrenching the digital divide. The risk of excluding parts of the population is particularly serious in the public sector due to its responsibility to offer inclusive public processes and services. There is also a risk that if the public health sector does not adopt new advanced technologies, then the benefits will be limited to those who can afford to pay for them privately.

⁴ Agudo U, Matute H (2021) The influence of algorithms on political and dating decisions. PLoS ONE 16(4): e0249454. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0249454>

2.1.4 Social isolation

Some DTs might affect the integrity of interpersonal dialogue, meaningful human connection, and social cohesion, consequently having an impact also on the capability of a person to flourish and to fully develop herself. This may depend on various factors, e.g. users may be led by convenience, habit or the marketing strategies and customisation adopted in providing services to use DTs for too long and become addicted to them, or even to replace human relations with man-machine relations. In general, an increase in time spent in a virtual world may correspond to a decrease in time spent in the real world with other people. This may decrease empathy, reduce human contacts (for instance in retail and service provision), undermining social cohesion and leading to social isolation.

This has special relevance for the public sector since human contacts in the public sector (social security and healthcare personnel) are particularly important for vulnerable people who are at risk of social isolation. In healthcare, reductions of human contacts are particularly problematic. Patients who are anxious and/or have a serious disease need to discuss their situation with empathetic physicians and nurses. There are also needs for human contacts in other parts of the public sector. Even a rejection of an application for a building permit or a tax deduction may be easier to understand in communications with a human being who has an abode and pays taxes than with an ever so well-informed chatbot.

2.1.5 Psychological harm

Some disruptive technologies can induce changes in human behaviour that are potentially deleterious to mental health. The same factors that lead to the risk of social isolation can have psychological effects and negative effects on mental health: for instance, people may become addicted to using a technology, and human relations can be replaced by human-machine relations, or the time spent in a virtual world can lead to a decrease in the time spent in the real world with other people in normal social interaction. .

Some phenomena of DTs generating psychological problems, or entrench existing ones, have been identified in the literature. For example:

- “The Attention Economy”: The increasing monetization of human attention, in ways that negatively impact the cognitive, emotional, and physical health of individuals, create risks of technological addiction, and correlate with economic and productivity losses;
- Abuse and Manipulation: Data and data processing can be manipulated, for instance in order to create an incorrect impression of public opinion or of actions that people take. This could generate psychological problems related to the definition of one's identity as well as personal fulfilment, and also steer public opinion in extremist directions that undermine the integrity of public decision making and democracy.
- Risk of overuse: Over reliance on and extensive use of DT solutions can have negative effects, leading for instance to apathy, and - in the long run - loss of specific skills.

2.1.6 Physical harm

Some disruptive technologies can physically harm human beings. This applies to autonomous machines such as robots that can be programmed, either by mistake or malevolent intent, to harm their users or other human beings. This risk is amplified in the case of technologies employing machine learning because the evolutionary trajectories of such technologies can be difficult to predict. The change in people's habits that may be brought about by some disruptive technologies may also cause physical harm to users (e.g. increased risk of disease due to sedentary habits induced by the technology).

3 Legal risks

3.1 Illegal behaviour

There are many mechanisms leading to illegal behaviour in connection with DTs. One potential such mechanism is connected with the tendency for legal frameworks for disruptive technologies to lag behind technological development, leading to legal gaps and uncertainties. This risk is particularly large if several countries are involved (cross-border). For example, in the European context different member countries can adopt different rules, which can give rise to a complex and partly unpredictable legal situation, in particular if the legal situation on the overarching EU level is not sufficiently clear.

3.2 Liability risks

The legal framework for emerging technologies often lags behind their application. In the absence of specific provisions, legal liability is difficult to foresee, and organizations may not be able to manage liability risks appropriately (e.g. by putting in place the proper insurance to protect against liability risks). The responsibility for failures or inappropriate decisions can be difficult to determine. This applies in particular if decisions are not based on pre-decided criteria (as is usually the case if machine learning is applied) and if there are no designated humans-in-the-loop across the entire process. Furthermore, if the distribution of responsibility between the manufacturer, the service provider and the user of a technology has not been determined beforehand, all parties run a risk of unexpected accountability for failures of the technology.

3.3 Lack of certification procedures

Standards and certification procedures have an important role in ensuring that technological products are predictable and reliable. Although industry standards are not parts of the legal system, their use in contracts accords to them a particular legal significance, and they are often considered as components of “soft law”. In the public sector, standards and certifications have a prominent role in the procurement of technology from commercial companies.

For new technologies, however, standards are usually lacking. In fact, standards, frameworks and audit procedures are under development and not available yet (see for reference the IEEE Artificial Intelligence Systems (AIS) Related Standards⁵). The lack of such global standards is also reflected within organisations that do not have established procedures to audit DT-based applications and lack the skills required to define new frameworks.

The use of technologies whose functioning has not been independently verified imposes risks of unclear liabilities in case of technological failures.

4 Governance risks

4.1 Use for unintended purposes

Like any technological device, disruptive technologies can be used for unintended purposes. For instance, a machine learning program can be applied to a database that is too small or otherwise unsuitable. Even if this is done with the best intentions, it can lead to unreliable conclusions. This risk depends in part on whether appropriate warning signals are incorporated into the program, as well as on the education of the personnel using the technology and the information about the technology they receive.

⁵ <https://standards.ieee.org/initiatives/artificial-intelligence-systems/standards.html>

4.2 Lack of transparency and explainability

Partly due to trade secrets and partly due to the unpredictability and complexity of the analytical techniques behind DTs, the outcomes of many uses of disruptive technologies are difficult to trace back to relevant criteria, or to explain in terms of the purpose of the process. This will happen when the decision process and responsibilities are poorly documented and when the system has been set up in a way that gives priority to protecting the product against imitations rather than to ensuring accountability and transparency.

Different aspects of DT solutions raise these kinds of risks. Namely:

- Lack of transparency and poor communication: lack of clarity about what kind of DT is used, how the decision process is structured, who is responsible for the development, use and management, the purpose and scope of the DT solution. All this can lead to lack of trust and misuse of the DT solution. For example, users may not be aware that they are interacting with DT-based applications and/or lack information about the system's capabilities and limitations. The risk of poor communication arises also from the usage of too technical language and incorrect level of details for the target audience.
- Unexplainable or unjustifiable outcomes: Lack of adequate information about algorithms and technologies behind DTs results in the poor understanding of how the applications function. Such applications, are not trustworthy.
- Lack of traceability, poor data & model management: fast-evolving DTs can make traceability challenging, and the speed at which they evolve can result in errors manifesting on a large scale, in a very short space of time. Auditing them will also be difficult.
- Closed source software: traditionally, software has been distributed in executable files, without access to the source code. This means that the user has no chance of discovering features such as deliberately introduced backdoors that can be used by an attacker to access the system.

The risks of unexplainability are particularly important in the public sector, since we presume that individuals have the right to know the grounds of the decisions affecting them. It would follow from this that individuals who are affected by a public decision based on automatized data processing should have access to clear information on how the decision was made (for instance if automated decision making was used) and on its justification. An additional reason why citizens should have access to this type of information is that otherwise they cannot exercise their right to appeal decisions and hold decision makers accountable.

4.3 Poor human oversight

When disruptive technologies are used to make or propose decisions, there is a risk of insufficient human oversight and control. Such risks are particularly large when the decision criteria are unclear or changing, as they will be when machine learning is applied. This may have particularly serious consequences for the public sector, due to its accountability to the citizens, and the strict demands of equal treatment and rule of the law that it has to adhere to.

4.4 Distrust

Citizens' mistrust in their elected officials and in the public administration is a prevalent feature in modern democracies. Making the socio-technological system more trustworthy is therefore an obvious and urgent priority in the protection and strengthening of democracy. The use of disruptive technologies can make this task more difficult, in particular, if there is a lack of transparency, and human decision-makers have been replaced or made less accessible.

4.5 Relations with the private sector

The potential risk arising from institutions relying on external parties to perform services or business activities on their behalf (the principal-agent problem) increases when dealing with disruptive technologies, since the

solutions are complex and often involve components from different sources. The control over commercial partners is limited, and it is often difficult to ensure that they follow ethical principles and put in place adequate controls. The buyer also runs the risk of a lock-in, i.e. committing to equipment or processes from a particular provider that make it difficult or costly to switch to another provider or to in-house development. This risk is in some cases exacerbated by the rules governing public sector procurement, which can make it difficult to take this factor into account in the choice among potential commercial providers.

4.6 Waste of resources

The development and adoption of DTs requires a considerable amount of effort in terms of economic resources and human time and work. On top of that, the innovative aspect of DT-based applications does not ensure the success of the initiatives, thus exacerbating the risk of wasting the allocated resources and effort.

In the public sector, the risk of wasting resources gains a higher relevance since resources are usually less available and they are gathered from public spending. At the same time, in public sector organisations a set of factors make this risk more probable, namely:

- Usually, public sector organisations lack a clear strategic plan for the adoption of DTs, which provides a clear direction and long-term goals;
- If the plan exists, it is rarely coordinated between the various actors involved, clearly communicated, implemented and monitored over time;
- The organisational structures and management roles usually do not have deep understanding of the DT and work in an environment with poor innovation culture;
- There is unclear accountability for and monitoring over investments in DTs.

4.7 Unclear accountability and responsibilities

The adoption of DTs creates challenges in terms of moral accountability and responsibility (in addition to issues of legal liability, see 2.2 above). Unless there are responsible humans-in-the-loop across the entire design and implementation chain, and activity monitoring protocols are clearly established prior to the DT design, it might not be clear who is ultimately responsible for each step of DT design, development, monitoring, and redesign, especially in federated models that allow for distributed responsibility. The risk just mentioned could be defined as unclear task responsibility.

5 Enhanced inequality and discrimination

5.1 Concentration of power

Currently, technological development tends to concentrate wealth and power in the hands of very few. New technological markets are highly competitive, but in the information economy, once a company achieves clear market leadership, it can often obtain a *de facto* monopoly, making it almost invulnerable to competition. All the well-known risks of monopolies apply, including risks of inefficiency and misuse of power. *De facto* monopolies are problematic for the public sector since it has to make use of their technologies, thereby fuelling the concentration of power. Companies with multinational market dominance often have the capability to elude national controls and rules, which means that the public sector can find itself to be the weaker partner in the relation.

5.2 Biased outcomes

When machine learning agents are trained on a biased material, they will produce a biased output. Potential sources of biases at data level are represented by historical human biases hidden in input data, incomplete or

unrepresentative training data, sampling errors and unbalanced protected attributes and proxies. While machine learning agents might not create new bias, they will perpetuate and solidify an already existing one.

Similar problems can arise if the datasets are too small for analysis, even if they are not biased.⁶ The old saying in computer science “garbage in, garbage out”, has been restated in machine learning as “bias in, bias out”. In medicine and law enforcement, machine learning has exacerbated ingrained patterns of discrimination of ethnic minorities. Bias and discrimination tend to be both self-fulfilling and self-reinforcing, and disruptive technologies can contribute to the perpetuation of these processes.

Furthermore, biases may also be present at the algorithm level. For example, sample selection bias might occur when conditioning on some variables in the dataset during data analysis takes place and it generates spurious correlations, confounding bias might emerge when dealing with proxy or omitted variables, and design-related biases might also be present due to limitations or constraints of the computer system and may result in ranking or representation biases.

Poor diversity of the development teams could also exacerbate these risks since it will be difficult for them to represent or anticipate the full diversity of human needs and values.

The risk of discrimination is particularly problematic for the public sector due to the high demands of equal treatment that it has to satisfy.

5.3 Unequal access and benefit

The use of new technologies usually requires economic and technological resources, as well as education. There is a risk that the growing economic gaps both between and within countries will be exacerbated by unequal access to the positive effects of disruptive technologies. Technologies often have to be adjusted to the different cultural environments where they will be used. Previous experience from other technologies shows that this is often not done in low-income countries, which can result in suboptimal use of technologies adjusted to other cultural conditions than those in which they are used.

5.4 Loss of cultural diversity

The global spread of new digital technologies such as smartphones, social media, and virtual assistants was led by a dominant Western culture, not least since most of these DTs were designed by in a relatively homogenous culture of technologists who lacked the resources needed to anticipate the full diversity of human needs and values.

As a consequence, wide DTs adoption might benefit large and already dominant cultures and art forms at the expense of local habits and forms of expression. This results in a risk that cultural expressions will be lost and the diversity of human culture diminished.

6 Errors and misuse

6.1 Unreliable or poor-quality outcomes

There are many types of technological problems that increase the risk of unreliable or poor-quality outcomes from disruptive technologies, for example lack of robustness, biased performance and security breaches.

As far as lack of robustness is concerned, changes in the context of application and changes to data can result in a decay of the performance of DT systems over time, leading to failed decision making or impacting the processes based on the DTs. Detection of this decay is paramount, and systems must be tested for resiliency

⁶ Taeihagh, Araz, M. Ramesh, and Michael Howlett. "Assessing the regulatory challenges of emerging disruptive technologies." *Regulation & Governance* (2021).

against performance drift both pre- and post- deployment. DTs may suffer from e.g. Concept Drift (when the relationship between input and output data changes over time), Brittleness (when DTA performance collapses following minor tweaks to data inputs), both of which affect the robustness and stability of data over time. Not performing ad hoc testing or failing to control the performances over time entails significant risks for organisations.

Another problem which may lead to unreliable or poor-quality outcomes is model overfitting, i.e. that the model works well on the training data but fails when new data with more variety or diminished quality is introduced. This is a persistent risk for uses of DTs that are autonomous or employ machine learning techniques. For this last type of DTs, also uncontrolled learning might represent a mayor risk, given the possibility of misdirected reinforcement learning behaviour, when errors arise from incorrect behaviours that are erroneously reinforced during the training phase.

Anther issue that can impact the quality of DTs is the use of “self-service” tools or easy-to-use tools for DT development by non-expert users. These tools allow people not properly trained in the best development practices to develop DT solutions, with obvious risks of malfunctioning or otherwise substandard outcomes.

In general, malfunctioning can result from the use of of untested and/or insufficiently managed software (either closed or open software). If software is continuously changed without rigorous retesting, the quality and stability of the source code can degenerate. This results in a more complicated governance and exposure to performance risks.

6.2 Autonomous weapons proliferation

Many disruptive technologies have the potential to be used as parts of weapon systems. In some cases weapons can be programmed to independently make life-or-death decisions. The proliferation of autonomous weapons poses a major threat to public security, if they are used by rogue states, terrorists or other criminals. Even their use in the armed forces of democratic nations gives rise to risks stemming from their autonomy and potential destructiveness.

6.3 Malicious surveillance

Some disruptive technologies can be used for surveillance systems that can be applied for unethical purposes. A totalitarian government can use surveillance systems to control the population.

Surveillance systems can also be used by employers for undue control of their employees or by tech companies for privacy-intrusive information collection from their customers. In this case, we can talk about a new ‘Digital Taylorism’⁷, which consists in new digital forms of ‘scientific management’ and control of workplace behaviour, in ways that can be dehumanizing, demoralizing, and destructive to mental health.

6.4 Disinformation

False news, misinformation and hoaxes spread quickly on the Internet. This can lead to disorientation of public opinion on important issues, and sometimes also to dangerous actions. Disruptive technologies can contribute to such developments by targeting communications to users selected to be particularly sensitive to particular messages. Such technologies can be used for commercial purposes, but also to disseminate disinformation and propaganda intended to influence voting behaviour. Such disinformation can mislead consumers to buy products that they would not have bought if better informed. It can also be used to sow hatred and initiate political processes that threaten democracy.

6.5 Democratic deficit

Disruptive technologies are developed in private companies, often multinational companies, which move their operations between countries in the way that best suits their interests. Consequently, parliaments, governments

⁷ <https://www.scu.edu/ethics-in-technology-practice/overview-of-ethics-in-tech-practice/>

and public sector organizations often find themselves in a situation of *fait accompli*: The major technological choices that should have been made in the public interest, for instance concerning privacy and customer influence, have already been made when the new technologies become the subject of public discussions and democratic decision-making. In other words, there is a risk of a technology-induced democratic deficit that limits the decision-making power of the citizens.

6.6 Citizen scoring

The term “citizen scoring” is often used in a purely descriptive and domain-specific sense, referring for instance to school systems, e-learning and driver licences. Nevertheless, applying these DT-enabled scoring systems, which assign a score to each citizen on the basis of which he or she will be granted a benefit or subjected to some disadvantage, might exacerbate existing inequalities, generate new ones and be detrimental to human rights. This might be so, especially if the scores refer to measures that are subject to human or machine judgement, and if important benefits or major disadvantages are involved. Transparency about the processes and criteria of scoring are essential, but does not guarantee of fairness and freedom of choice. Ideally the possibility of opting out of the scoring mechanism without detriment should be provided⁸.

7 Security and data protection risks

7.1 Rogue applications

Disruptive technologies can be used for illegal and anti-social purposes. Media technology can be used to disseminate hateful messages that threaten the security of the targets of these messages. Artificial intelligence has been used to discover undercover police officers in order to protect illegal activities. Technological products can be developed for such purposes. However, products developed for legitimate purposes can often be used for purposes they were not designed to serve. The risk that a new technology can be used for illegal or discriminatory purposes will in part depend on how large efforts have been made to reduce or eliminate its usefulness for such purposes.

7.2 Hacking to change the behaviour of the DT

Many disruptive technologies are sensitive to data poisoning and adversarial attacks aimed at changing the system’s functioning, for instance in order to create chaos or cause an accident. Data poisoning is the malicious compromise of data sources in the stages concerning data collection and pre-processing, while adversarial attack, by way of example on machine learning models, maliciously modify input data to induce them into misclassification or incorrect prediction. The severity of a potential adversarial attack depends on the nature of the system. For example, disaster would follow if autonomous cars were hacked to make them collide.

Such attacks can be directed against the public sector as well as against individuals, companies, and other organizations.⁹ Infrastructure systems have often been pointed out as high risks in this respect. The likelihood of a successful adversarial attack depends to a high degree on the cybersecurity systems that are in use, but also on measures to prevent malicious insider activities.

7.3 Hacking to get information access

Cyberintrusion can also take place in order to collect sensitive data. The public sector keeps large amounts of data that is sensitive – from defence information to data about individual persons. Risks of intrusion increase with data reuse and interconnectedness e.g. when a database containing sensitive information is accessible to

⁸ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (HLEG), “Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI”, 8 April 2019. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/196377/AI%20HLEG_Ethics%20Guidelines%20for%20Trustworthy%20AI.pdf

⁹ Leitner, Christine, and Christian M. Stiefmueller. “Disruptive technologies and the public sector: the changing dynamics of governance.” *Public Service Excellence in the 21st Century*. Palgrave Macmillan, Singapore, 2019. 237-274.

officials in public agencies. Data breaches in public sector domains is very common, and in some cases attempts at blackmailing have been directed at the public sector. To prevent successful illicit access to personal sensitive data continuously updated cybersecurity measures are necessary.

7.4 Loss of service continuity

Loss of connectivity for instance due to power failure or software malfunction, may lead to service disruptions that shut out users from essential services when they are most urgently needed. Interruptions hitting public services, particularly health and other essential services, can have serious consequences. The risk of such interruptions depends to a large degree on how much redundancy is built into the system.

8 Unsustainable use

8.1 High level of energy consumption

Increased computational complexity requires more resources in terms of memory, computational power and time. This is reflected also in the energy consumption of data centres. Energy consumption (although strictly speaking not a risk, since it is a predictable and quantifiable effect of computing) should be an increasingly important factor in the design of disruptive technologies.

8.2 Use of environmentally unsustainable materials

Some of the materials used in the production of disruptive technologies are not environmentally sustainable. In particular, rare materials are used in electronic devices. Many of them are extracted in unsafe and environmentally destructive mines in already over-exploited areas of the planet.

9 Workplace issues

9.1 Job displacement

Increased automation will reduce the need for simple, repetitive tasks, requiring fewer people to work. This will have impacts on the labour market and on the need for education of the workforce. If not properly dealt with, it can lead to increased poverty and reduced social cohesion.

9.2 Lack of competences

Disruptive technologies require skills and competences that are usually not widespread in workplaces in the public sector. Without appropriate training and recruitment policies, the public sector will lack many of the key competences needed to implement the new technologies in an appropriate way.

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